

Appendix 2: Description of search for an existing review

Before drafting the protocol, I searched to see if there is a systematic review that has already answered the research question: What is the quality of news media reports about the effects and costs of health interventions? The question is interdisciplinary. However, I consider it unlikely that such a review has been published in a journal focused on journalism. This is based on my experience and knowledge from studying and working in both journalism and health research. Moreover, I was aware of more than 30 potentially eligible primary studies before searching for an existing review (Appendix 1), and all of those studies were published in the health-focused databases that I searched.

Specifically, I searched the meta-databases Epistemonikos (www.epistemonikos.org) and Trip Pro (www.tripdatabase.com). These include PubMed (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed), the Cochrane Library (www.cochranelibrary.com) and Prospero (www.crd.york.ac.uk/prospero). It is unlikely that a health-related systematic review with such broad relevance would be missing from such large databases of health-related systematic reviews.

No limits were placed on time of publication or language. The Epistemonikos search was limited to titles and abstracts. The Trip Pro search was limited to titles only, since Trip Pro searches cannot be limited to abstracts. Neither Epistemonikos or Trip Pro have Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) functionality. In both searches, I only used terms for the population because I considered those terms sufficiently narrow, given that I could filter for systematic reviews.

I identified and selected terms for the population in six steps. First, I checked for terms in the titles of potentially eligible studies. Second, I broke down compounds (e.g. “news media reports”) into smaller terms (e.g. “news”, “media” and “reports”). Third, I checked a thesaurus for synonyms. Fourth, I listed the smaller terms and what I considered common synonyms. Fifth, I placed the list along both the top and left side of a table, and considered all possible combinations, excluding those that are nonsensical or uncommon (Appendix 2a). Finally, I selected terms from the table, considering: 1) how likely it was that someone would have used the given term to describe the population in a review

answering the research question; and 2) how many irrelevant search results using the term would add.

I got feedback from an information specialist on an initial draft of the search strategy, then conducted test searches. In some cases, the test searches were for single terms. Some of those single terms, such as “media” and “mass media”, were excluded from the final searches. Including them would have added a large number of irrelevant search results—for example reviews related to (mass) media interventions, such as interventions for smoking cessation—and I considered it unlikely that a review answering the research question would exclude all of the remaining terms from its title.

The only difference between the terms used in the Epistemonikos and Trip Pro searches was that “the news” was excluded from the Trip Pro search (Table A1). Excluding the term reduced the results by over 1000. The problem appears to have been that the engine automatically and irreversibly included similar, but inaccurate and broad terms, including “new”.

The final Epistemonikos search resulted in 89 entries categorised as systematic reviews (Appendix 2b). The final Trip Pro search resulted in 48 (Appendix 2c). Both searches were executed on Feb. 19, 2018. Neither resulted in a systematic review answering the research question.

To test my assumption about the (un)likelihood of there being a systematic review answering the question in a journal focused on journalism, I searched Google Scholar (www.scholar.google.com) on the same date, screening the first 50 results. Since there is a Google Scholar searches have a character limit, I only used “news” to describe the population, while adding “health” and “systematic review” (Table A1). Limiting the search to titles (i.e. typing “allintitle:” ahead of the search terms) only resulted in one entry, which did not answer the research question. Removing said limit increased the results to 6990 entries. Of the first 50, most were in health-focused or health-related journals, several were familiar from Epistemonikos and Trip Pro searches, and none answered the research question.

In addition to the database searches, I consulted with four other researchers who have done studies related to the quality of health journalism, and who have taught “evidence-based” health journalism. Three are co-authors of studies potentially eligible primary studies. They were all unaware of a systematic review answering the research question.

Table A1: Terms used to search for an existing systematic review answering the research question

Database	Query
Epistemonikos	(title:(("media coverage" OR "news coverage" OR "press coverage" OR "fourth estate" OR "media information" OR "news items" OR journalis* OR "lay media" OR "news media" OR "health news" OR "the news" OR "media outlets" OR "news outlets" OR "press outlets" OR "lay press" OR "popular press" OR "the press" OR "media reporting" OR "news reporting" OR "media reports" OR "news reports" OR "media sources" OR "news sources" OR "health stories" OR "media stories" OR "news stories")) OR abstract:(("media coverage" OR "news coverage" OR "press coverage" OR "fourth estate" OR "media information" OR "news items" OR journalis* OR "lay media" OR "news media" OR "health news" OR "the news" OR "media outlets" OR "news outlets" OR "press outlets" OR "lay press" OR "popular press" OR "the press" OR "media reporting" OR "news reporting" OR "media reports" OR "news reports" OR "media sources" OR "news sources" OR "health stories" OR "media stories" OR "news stories")))
Trip Pro	title:(("media coverage" OR "news coverage" OR "press coverage" OR "fourth estate" OR "media information" OR "news items" OR journalis* OR "lay media" OR "news media" OR "health news" OR "media outlets" OR "news outlets" OR "press outlets" OR "lay press" OR "popular press" OR "the press" OR "media reporting" OR "news reporting" OR "media reports" OR "news reports" OR "media sources" OR "news sources" OR "health stories" OR "media stories" OR "news stories"))
Google Scholar	health "systematic review" "news media"